

Which Way West Africa? The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and its Efforts of Peacekeeping in the Region: Lessons from the Past and Prospects for the Future.

Abstract

Regional integration in Africa didn't start with ECOWAS, regional integration initiatives started with the establishment of the South African Customs Union (SACU) in 1910 and the East African Community in 1919. Since then, a number of regional economic initiatives have been undertaken and every African country belongs to an economic community.

ECOWAS was established in May 1975 in Lagos by the signing of the ECOWAS Treaty. It was believed to be the answer to the question of economic and regional integration.

In understanding the experience of ECOWAS since its formation, some might say the road has not been an easy one. This creates an array of questions.

What is ECOWAS and the rationale behind its establishment?

Why did ECOWAS involve itself in the maintenance of peace and security in West Africa?

How effective were the peacekeeping measures of past conflicts?

Are there problems involved in achieving this goal?

Which way forward?

Premised on these questions, this essay is set to discuss the rationale behind the establishment of ECOWAS, evolution, measures taken by ECOWAS to foster peace and stability, Past interventions of ECOWAS in Mali, Liberia and Côte d'Ivoire. It also takes a step further to analyze the problems and prospects associated with achieving peace and security, as a means of understanding the way forward.

Keywords: ECOWAS, Peacekeeping, Security, Regional Organization, Prospects.

Introduction

After the political independence of African countries from colonial rule in the 1960s, these countries realized that they had to pool their resources together, to attain economic independence too. This will later form the basis for the establishment of ECOWAS.

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) is an economic union comprising of fifteen (15) West African Countries. It was a regional organization aimed at facilitating peace, security, economic growth and development in the West Africa State (Adetula, 2009).

ECOWAS was established on the 28th of May, 1975, with the signing of the treaty of Lagos.

Subsequently, the treaty of Lagos was revised and signed on the 24th of July, 1993 in Cotonou.

It should be noted that ECOWAS is one of the regional blocs of the African

Economic Community (AEC). Member countries that make up ECOWAS are, The Benin Republic, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Senegal and Togo (Afolabi, 2012).

Also, the new Pan-Africanism which emerged as a political and cultural movement in the early nineteenth century, regards Africa's sub-regional bodies as invaluable instruments in actualising the new African agenda (Landsberg & Mckay, 2005).

Can we see the establishment of ECOWAS in this light?, As a response to the demands of Pan-Africanism.

Since its establishment for economic integration, it's no news that it has indulged in peacekeeping actions in the region. Some might say it's a shift from its aim of economic integration, others might say it's a response to the West African problem with a West African Solution or that indulging in peacekeeping efforts is another measure for fostering integration.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this essay is the Structural Functionalist Theory. This theory was propounded by Herbert Spencer, and later developed by Talcott Parsons, Émile Durkheim and Robert Merton.

In reference to this theory, it can be asserted that the structures put in place by ECOWAS in her region are instrumental in ensuring peacebuilding, conflict management and security. Examples are ECOMOG (Economic Community of West African States Monitoring Group), West African Network for Peace Building (WANEP), West African Civil Society Forum (WACOSF). Through these measures in ensuring peace in West Africa, security is also attainable in the region.

It is not enough that these structures exist, they should function effectively and efficiently.

Rationale Behind the ECOWAS Intervention in Conflicting West African States.

Conflict is inevitable in the affairs of nation-states. As such, this discourse has gained momentum in academia.

West African states is no exception to this assertion.

In the early 1990s, after the establishment of ECOWAS, the region witnessed political instabilities and conflicts. States were infested by political and election crises and violent conflicts. Some of these states are Liberia, Sierra Leone and Côte d'Ivoire. During this period, it became increasingly necessary for interventions and conflict management, but none was coming at that time.

Rather, there was lukewarm responses from continental and global communities. With these happenings, there was a shift from the general orientation of ECOWAS for economic good, to the inclusion of peacekeeping and conflict management in her region.

The involvement of the organization in form of interventions, was the beginning of a new era for the organization, who in previous years have been saddled with the responsibility of ensuring economic development.

Therefore, the involvement of ECOWAS opened a new panorama for the organization as an essential means of accomplishing and attaining regional peace and security (Golwa, 2009).

During this situation of conflict, there was a tepid response from the United Nations.

ECOWAS had to resort to West African Solution to a West African Peace and Security problem, experimented using ECOMOG as a launch pad (Ero, 2000). This initiative by ECOWAS exposes a new stance in the involvement of regional organizations in peace and conflict.

The United Nation, through her former secretary General, Boutros Ghali commented to this effect.

He proposed that; Regional action, however, could lighten the burden of the council and contribute to a deeper sense of participation, consensus and democratization in international affairs. Consultations between the United Nations and regional arrangements or agencies

could do much to build international consensus on the nature of a problem and the measures required to address it (Ghali, 1992)

According to (Galadima, 2006; Golwa, 2009), it was the Liberian conflict that led to the establishment of ECOMOG as the first peace keeping and peace enforcement mission set up by a regional economic body in the world. In 1990, an ECOMOG force with membership drawn from Gambia, Ghana, Nigeria and Sierra Leone, were put in place, to foster peace and stability in Liberia.

It should also be noted that (Nwankwo, 2010), asserted that the emergence of ECOMOG as a regional strategy for reacting to the multifaceted emergency in West African states, was premised on the notion that regional peace, security, stability, unity, mutual relations and trust and good neighborliness were necessary for achieving the ultimate aims and objectives of ECOWAS.

Measures Taken by ECOWAS to Foster Peace and Stability

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) collaborated with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), in ensuring peace and stability. This measure is a germane part of her strategy for conflict resolution and peacekeeping efforts.

Some of these CSOs are West African Network for Peace Building (WANEP), West African Civil Society Forum (WACOSF), West African Action Network on Small Arms (WAANSA). The establishment of election units by the organization created an opportunity for more robust partnership between ECOWAS and civil societies in the region, through the WACOSF (Adebanjo, 2004). The partnership between ECOWAS and the civil society was anchored on the fact that civil society possesses the ability to make informed inputs into the peacebuilding initiatives in West Africa (Opoku, 2007)

Another measure undertaken by ECOWAS in ensuring conflict management, peace building and stability in West Africa is evident through her peace keeping actions under the auspices of the ECOMOG. Her actions through this body served as a model for peacekeeping and conflict resolution in West Africa.

This model became a permanent part of the framework of conflict management and contained in the 1999 Protocol Relating to the Mechanism for Conflict Prevention, Management, Resolution, Peacekeeping, Peacebuilding and Security, used to contain conflicts in Guinea Bissau, Mali, Sierra Leone, Côte d'Ivoire and Gambia (Sessay, 2002). Consequently, member states of ECOWAS viewed ECOMOG more as a vehicle for defining their security apparatus.

Peacekeeping: ECOWAS Intervention in Mali, Liberia and Côte d'Ivoire

Mali Conflict of 2012

Mali's government was overthrown in a military coup and an Islam extremist group known as Al Qaeda, exerted control on the major towns in the north. This insurgency led to economic drain and displacement of citizens.

ECOWAS intervened in the conflict and this was necessitated by the various protocols on peace and security, agreed upon by all members of the organization (Afolabi, 2012)

Côte d'Ivoire's Political and Electoral Crises

The 2010-2011 crisis in Côte d'Ivoire began after President Laurent Gbagbo refused to accept election results, despite international recognition of Alassane as the winner, leading to the breakdown of state stability. The constitutional council disregarded votes garnered during the election. This action was condemned by ECOWAS, which influenced the Ivorian authority to accept the result.

Liberian Civil War

The Liberian civil war which took place in two periods, the first was from 1989 to 1997 and the second from 1999 to 2003. Charles Taylor's rebellious forces challenged President Doe and this led to the disruption of peace and stability in the country. According to (Afolabi, 2012), ECOWAS intervened and stopped the rebellion in Monrovia and exiled Charles Taylor to Nigeria, until he was arrested and taken in for his trial.

Way Forward: Problems and Prospects Associated with ECOWAS

In assessing the way forward, one must take into consideration, the prospects of ECOWAS in a world bedeviled by a number of problems, which has limited its mode of operation.

Among these problems are; lack of commitment of member states in attaining its aims and objectives, political instability in the region arising from political crises and complicated by the recent lack of efforts by ECOWAS to enforce sanctions.

For example, Mali, Burkina Faso and Guinea now operate a military system of government and ECOWAS hasn't been able to enforce a sustainable solution to this issue. Also, the lack of unity between member states and allegiance to colonial masters as many member states will rather go into relations with their colonial masters than fellow member states.

Lack of financial support and funds to boost the operation of the organization. It is not news that no organization can function without being financed, the member states of the organization are faced with deteriorating economy and poverty.

Despite these problems confronting the organization, the prospects of the organization cannot be overlooked. The future of ECOWAS as regards effective peacekeeping and conflict management, can be linked to the embrace of its legitimacy by member states and the commitment of member states in achieving its aims and objectives.

How is this possible? According to some members of the ECOWAS Community Court of Justice, Sendarin and Zanku, (Sendarin, 2022, cited in Edodi, 2024; Zanku, 2022, cited in Edodi, 2024), political commitment and legitimacy will create the enabling environment for the institution to work optimally and make meaningful advancements towards the 2063 agenda of the AU.

Also, according to Offuya a member of the ECOWAS parliament, one of the challenges confronting and threatening the security of lives and property of member states of the ECOWAS is religious intolerance (Offuya, 2022, cited in Edodi, 2024).

Thus, by embracing the legitimacy of ECOWAS by member states, commitment of member states in achieving the organization's goals and addressing problems of religious intolerance amongst others, will bring a new dawn of peacekeeping efforts in the region.

Conclusion

This essay concludes that conflict is inevitable and with its ever-present nature in state relations, ECOWAS should address its shortcomings and advance towards achieving peace and security in the region. This is because in recent times, the organization is not as active in fostering peace and stability in the region.

Having examined the rationale behind the advent of its peacekeeping operations in the region, measures taken to foster peace, intervention in selected member states and challenges it is facing. It is imperative to note that the way forward for the organization, is to create sustainable frameworks and systems that will support the execution of the decisions made to achieve peace and security in the region. By sustainable framework, it means strong commitment of member states and legitimacy of the organization, a regional hegemon, propagation of common values, as these will promote peace and security in the region.

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